

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE CARDIO-THORACIC RATIO AND WEIGHT AMONG STUDENTS OF DELTA STATE UNIVERSITY, ABRAKA

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Abstract

Background: The cardio-thoracic ratio (CTR) is a method of practically determining the heart size by relating it to the total thoracic width and it is expressed as a ratio. The term body weight could be referred to the diet or physical activities the individual engages in. This study determined the relationship between an individual's CTR and weight. **Methods:** The study was carried out on 200 students of Delta State University, Abraka. Their chest radiographs were gotten and the CTR was measured and calculated. The weights of the individuals were also measured. **Results:** The research result presents that the correlation between CTR and weight is poor, with $r = 0.086$ and 0.115 for male and female respectively. **Conclusion:** This therefore shows that cardiothoracic ratio is least affected by the variations of body weight.

Keywords: Cardio-Thoracic Ratio; Weight; Abraka; Chest Radiographs.

INTRODUCTION

The cardio-thoracic ratio (CTR) is a long accepted method of quantifying cardiac size and carries prognostic information in acquired heart disease. CTR measures the ratio distance between the internal rib margins at the level of the right hemi-diaphragm to the maximal transverse diameter of the cardiac silhouette [1]. It is measured in percentage and could be affected by age. It is largest in neonates that have a CTR of 60% and in order men the CTR reduces by 0.3mm in approximate 5 years. A normal CTR is 50% [1].

Cardio-thoracic ratio has been a functional index of cardiac dilatation and a value of 50% is generally used to describe the upper limit of a normal cardiac size. However, this value increases the number of false-positive results in obese or older subjects with misdiagnosis of cardiac enlargement and the value always incorrect [2]. The diameters

of the left ventricle and the right atrium shown by x-ray and computed tomography indicated by the maximal transverse diameter of the cardiac shadow of chest x-ray film [2].

The term body weight refers to a person's mass or weight. It is usually taken to be the force of the body due to gravity. Body weight is one way of determining a person's health. The Average body weight for an adult is $60.7\text{kg} \pm 2.3\text{kg}$ [3].

The correlation between the cardiothoracic ration (CTR) and the weight is very important in the determination of a person's health and related heart disorders.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design: This is a quantitative cross sectional descriptive study.

Study Population: This study was composed of two hundred students of Delta State University, Abraka.

Ethical Clearance: Approval and content of the research was collected from the Anatomy Department Ethical Clearance Committee in the Delta State University, Abraka.

Subject Collection

Inclusion Criteria:

- i. Students of Delta State University, 2013/2014 session.
- ii. Normal and clear chest radiograph of the students.

Exclusion Criteria

- i. Presence of spinal deformity on radiograph
- ii. Abnormal and blurred radiograph
- iii. Radiographs with cardiomegaly

Materials for the Research

- i. Radiating light beams
- ii. Hands gloves
- iii. Laboratory coat
- iv. Data form
- v. Transparent measuring tape
- vi. Radiographs of students of Delta State University, 2013/2014 session.
- vii. Weight balance

METHODS

The data for this research work was collected at the University Health Centre, Delta State University (Delsu), Abraka, Delta State. The weight of the student of Delsu was taken and then chest X-rays of the individuals was also taken. The radiographs of the thorax were then placed on halogenated light beams to properly reflect the x-ray parts. Data was then collected with a calibrated ruler in centimeters and a pencil. The measure of the cardiac diameter and then thoracic diameter was taken and recorded in a data form. The data form comprised of columns for males, females, weight, cardiac diameter, thoracic diameter and CTR.

Measurement of Cardiac Diameter

The cardiac size was measured by first drawing parallel lines at the sides of the heart for clear demarcation and the measurement of distance between the two parallel lines were taken by transparent calibrated ruler.

Measurements of Thoracic Diameters

The thoracic width was measured by first drawing parallel lines on the inner aspect of the rib margins at the level of the hemi-diaphragm and the distance between them were measured by transparent calibrated ruler.

Figure 1: A View of the Measurement of the Cardiothoracic Diameter

Calculation of Cardio-thoracic Ratio (CTR)

CTR was calculated by the ratio of the Heart diameter (CD) to the Chest diameter as measured on chest radiography.

$$\text{CTR} = \frac{\text{Heart Diameter}}{\text{Chest Diameter}} \times 100$$

Precautions

- i. The positions measured were marked clearly before the measurements were taken.

- ii. Only clearly visible radiographs were used.
- iii. A repeat of each measurement was done for accuracy.

Data Analysis

In analyzing the collected data the following statistical methods were used: mean, range, standard deviation and correlation using chi-test method.

RESULTS

The total numbers of students used for this analysis were 200. The males made up 100 of the population size while the females made up the other 100.

Table 1: Statistical Frequency of the Cardio-Thoracic Ratio and Weight

Male	CTR	Weight
Valid	100	100
Mean	44.79	61.92
Median	44.80	63.00
Mode	44.80	63.00
Female		
Valid	100	100
Mean	46.76	60.54
Median	47.10	60.00
Mode	48.00	64.00

The statistical frequency of the distribution is given above in Table 1. The average CTR for an adult as indicated by this analysis was 46% ± 2%. While the average body weight for an adult is 60.7kg ± 2.3kg. Among the 200 students used for the analysis 103 had a CTR of over 46% and 116 of the sample size had a weight of over 60kg.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of the Cardio-Thoracic Ratio and Weight using the Mean Values and Their Standard Deviation

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Number
Male			100
CTR	44.79	2.94	
Weight	61.92	8.98	
Female			100
CTR	46.76	2.99	
Weight	60.54	8.94	

The mean CTR for the male population was 44.7% with a standard deviation of 2.9, while the mean weight is 61.9kg with a standard deviation of 8.9. The mean CTR for the female population was 46.7% with a standard deviation of 2.9, while the mean weight is 60.5kg with a standard deviation of 8.9. The descriptive statistics for the distribution is given above in table 2.

Table 3: Correlation between Cardio-Thoracic Ratio and Weight

Males		CTR	Weight
	Sig. (2-tailed)	-	.086

	Number	100	100
Female			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	-	.115
	Number	100	100

Using statistical software we calculated correlation coefficients between CTR and weight. This analysis showed that the relation between weight and CTR was poor or weak. The result is given in the table above, correlation significant of $p \leq 0.01$ level (2 tailed).

Table 4: Class Interval for CTR Calculated in Mean Values, CTR and Weight for both Sexes

	Class using CTR	Number	CTR mean	Weight mean
Male	< 40	3	38.33	59
	41-50	94	45.27	62.36
	> 50	3	50.43	56.33
Female	< 40	1	38.4	77
	41-50	89	46.45	60.36
	> 50	10	50.88	61.9

The average cardio-thoracic ratio in males was 44.79 ± 2.94 and females were 46.76 ± 2.99 . Results were showing a higher but not significant CTR in females at the $P = 0.01$ significance level.

DISCUSSION

Cardio-thoracic ratio (CTR) is a long accepted method of quantifying cardiac size. It carries information on likely causes of diseases in acquired heart [1]. The body weight of an individual refers to the person's mass which occur by diet or physical individual engages [3]. The relation between an individual's CTR and the individuals' weight go a long way in determining the person's health.

The result reported here shows that the correlation between CTR and weight are $r = 0.086$ for males and $r = 0.115$ for females which are too poor or too weak for it to be useful clinically as a diagnostic test to give the well-being of an individual, judging from the standard measure of the linear correlation, which states that the value of 'r' lies between -1 and 1, and that values closer to 0 indicate poor correlation.

Prior to this study, several observations had been made that the heart's size in normal cases is dependent principally on body build [4]. In a study carried out by Anyanwu et al., it was found out that there is a weak relationship between CTR and all the indices of the size of the body used in the study, such as Body Mass Index (BMI), weight, height and body surface area [5].

According to the research of Ekedigwe et al., to find out the relation between CTR and various body parameters revealed that the relation between the CTR and BMI in both sexes were very weak. However, they should be significant relationship between CTR and BMI but in this, study the reverse was the case [6].

This work is in line with Anyanwu et al., who observed that CTR is not a better index when predicting a person's health condition using the various dimension of body weight [5].

The findings of the present study are in conformity with the observation of Ekedigwe et al., who suggests that when the CTR is complemented with the ultrasonography, echocardiography and magnetic resonance imaging of the heart then fully assessment of the patient could have be done [6].

I had proposed in the significance of the study that the relation of individual's cardio-thoracic radio and the individual's weight will go a long way in determining the person's health but I failed to established this because of the weak correlation value $r = 0.086$ and 0.115 for male and female respectively. In applying for the CTR this should be noted; CRT is abnormal when is above 50% and normal when is not up to 50%.

CONCLUSION

This research reports show that CTR is least affected by the variation of dimension of body's weight. This indicates that the relation between CTR and weight are not significantly correlated for the results to be presented clinically as a diagnostic test to determine the well-being of an individual.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declared no conflict of interest

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